

**STUDENT LEADERS AND PSYCHOLOGY PROFESSORS'
COMMITMENT AND SATISFACTION: BASIS FOR
DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM**

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Student Leaders and Psychology Professors' Commitment and Satisfaction: Basis for Development Program

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Abstract

This study aimed to see if there was a correlation and differences between the commitment and satisfaction of Psychology Society Officers and Psychology Professors. The respondents' demographic profiles are age, sex, and job title. For the 2019–2022 school year, this research analyzed the responses to a survey of six psychology professors and twenty-one Psychology Society Officers of the Psychological Society using a correlational-comparative methodology. Based on the findings, commitment has a significant relationship to the satisfaction of the Psychology Society Officers with Pearson r 0.67 and a p -value of 0.000. The analysis revealed that commitment has no significant relationship to the satisfaction of the Psychology Professors with Pearson r 0.18 and p -value of 0.729. The commitment of Psychology Society Officers has no significant relationship to the commitment of the Psychology Professors with Pearson r 0.12 and p -value of 0.825, and the satisfaction of Psychology Society Officers has no significant relationship to the satisfaction of the Psychology Professors with Pearson r -0.65 and p -value of 0.166. Lastly, the commitment of Psychology Society Officers has a significant difference to the commitment of the Psychology Professors with a p -value of 0.000. Furthermore, the analysis revealed that satisfaction of Psychology Society Officers has a significant difference to the satisfaction of the Psychology Professors with a p -value of 0.023.

Keywords: *psychology society officers, psychology professors, commitment and satisfaction*

Introduction

Employees' level of contentment with their work is referred to as job satisfaction. In addition to their day-to-day tasks, this includes their interactions with supervisors and colleagues, their thoughts on the policies and procedures of the company, and how their job impacts their personal lives (BasuMallick, 2021). A person's dedication to their work is defined as their ownership of the organization's purpose and objectives. An employee's dedication to their work increases the likelihood that they will do the things that the firm needs them to do to reach its goals. Knowing own strengths and weaknesses is crucial if the individual want to succeed as an employee or leader. Utilizing the strengths allows people to produce the best work, which is satisfying. The job and personal pleasure will increase if the people consistently play to the abilities.

School administrators, during the COVID-19 pandemic, need to keep their students' mental and physical health in mind, communicate effectively, and be adaptable. Like other parts of society, school organizations and their leaders face the executive duties outlined by Boin et al. (2013). Some of the leaders during the pandemic are assuming positions without ever having seen their coworkers or employees in person while providing services to students they can only reach via technology and who have all encountered some level of stress or anxiety due to the pandemic's obstacles. Leadership entrance is always intimidating, but it's particularly risky right now (Adhikary, 2017).

Education has become one of the most often used measures of progress. Producing educated workers who can meet the development problems faced by a firm is one of education's main aims. A happy staff in the industry is essential for this to succeed. Workers who like what they do for a living are more invested in their work and produce better results (Scott, 2004). Many researchers are interested in studying workers' attitudes toward work. Because pleased workers perform better, it is the top responsibility of all firms to increase their satisfaction to accomplish the intended goals (Kousteliou, 2001).

An educator is someone who works with students one-on-one to help them understand complex concepts, develop their skills, and apply what they've learned. A teacher is someone who works in a classroom setting and is responsible for translating educational philosophy and goals into students' actual knowledge and skill sets. Formal teaching takes place in a classroom setting, where instructors guide and support student learning (Ofoegbu, 2004). One of the crucial components of school education is the role of educators in making this a reality. Therefore, educators have a pivotal role in shaping their pupils' personal and monetary growth. Their knowledge, talent, and attitude must be offered, and they must commit themselves professionally. The quality of the educational system, including the instructors' commitment, happiness, and motivation, determines the extent to which students benefit from it. Teachers serve as examples to follow since they are the backbone of society (Jyoti & Sharma, 2009). They guide students in their personal development and prepare them to take charge of their country's future.

Research Questions

The following research questions are intended to be addressed in this study by using the correlational study methodology:

1. To what extent do the following describe the respondent demographics:
 - 1.1. age;

- 1.2. sex; and
- 1.3. job title?
2. How do the student leaders and psychology professors rate their commitment?
3. How do the student leaders and psychology professors rate their satisfaction?
4. Is there a correlation between the satisfaction and commitment of the psychology professors and the student leaders?
5. Is there a difference between satisfaction and commitment of the student leaders and psychology professors?
6. What kind of development program might be put in place to deal with the respondents' level of satisfaction and commitment?

Literature Review

Commitment, and Job Satisfaction of Students

U.S. Department of Labor Statistics data from 2008 shows that students who work part-time often have better grade point averages than those who are unemployed. Given that their time is divided between employment or other activities and schoolwork's, students who work or participate in other extracurricular activities may have superior time management skills than those who do not. The use of these abilities could therefore improve academic success. Furthermore, students may have the opportunity to meet and develop connections with supervisors and other staff members while working (Kulm & Cramer, 2006). Students' overall performance may improve if they are able to build social networks because of employment opportunities. A student's growth can only be positively influenced by interactions that are helpful and supportive.

Academics and professional achievement may take a hit when relationships with important people, including supervisors, are strained. Possibilities for gainful employment are associated with positive social development, which in turn may boost one's sense of feelings of worth. Since connections and self-worth are discovered to be linked, learners' feelings of worth could grow as they cultivate excellent working relationships (Mund & Neyer, 2016). Despite a wealth of literature examining employee-supervisor relationships and job satisfaction for adults, a more nuanced examination of particular factors, such as the student's connection with a direct supervisor and the learner's general satisfaction with the work, could shed light on the potential benefits of employment for students (Dulebohn et al., 2012).

Using the Leader-Member Exchange Theory as a lens, we looked at how different aspects of students' jobs affected their happiness on the job. According to research conducted by Dulebohn et al. (2012), the Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) model posits a distinct interaction of factors that lead to general contentment with one's employment, productivity in the workplace, and constructive actions taken by the organization. Leadership style and personality traits are two of the variables that may be used to forecast several outcomes in the workplace (Liden & Maslyn, 1998). An examination of the leader-follower dynamic was the initial motivation for developing the LMX model (Graen & Scandura, 1987). Because every leader-member relationship is different, this model was also developed with that in mind. Moderators and mediators of the leader-follower dynamic are now part of the LMX model (Dulebohn et al., 2012). Examples of factors that could affect the LMX dynamic include trust in interpersonal interactions, leader-type traits (such as leadership style), and follower-related personality variables (such as competence). The results could be negative for job performance (e.g., turnover) or positive (e.g., increased happiness at work) depending on the LMX quality.

Pattie et al. (2013) and Peterson et al. (2012) cite recent studies that provide credence to the LMX model's central tenet: that factors contributing to leader-member exchange—including follower traits and leader qualities—and interpersonal relationships—are crucial to work satisfaction. Financial and accounting experts surveyed 150 C-suite executives from the top corporations in the country for a 2003 report that appeared in the Westchester County Business Journal. Among the most essential elements that subordinates appreciated were open lines of communication, empowerment, and recognition of accomplishments; in fact, these factors were more valuable to workers than rewards. Employees report higher levels of job satisfaction when they can influence organizational choices via their leaders' actions and when there is open communication between leaders and their teams. Ronen and Mikulincer (2012) used full-time staff in their investigation, which further supports this conclusion. Employees reported higher levels of job satisfaction when they had positive connections with their supervisors, according to one study. Research by Gilstrap and Collins (2012) also relies on data acquired from professionals working for a big industrial company. Employees reported higher levels of job satisfaction when they had confidence in their boss. The significance of leaders sustaining high-quality relationships with supervisors is emphasized by these results (Liao, Hu, & Chung, 2009). Concerning issues like financial requirements and long-term objectives, students may vary from adults in their motives for working. Because of the many ways in which working affects young people, including their relationships, self-efficacy, and academic performance, and because there may be distinctions between student and adult employees.

Commitment and Job Satisfaction of Professors

Armstrong (2006) defines work satisfaction as people's attitudes and sentiments regarding their jobs. When it comes to attitudes about work and the workplace, positive or favorable attitudes show job satisfaction, whereas negative or unfavorable attitudes point to job unhappiness. Because of teacher job satisfaction, Zembylas, M., and Papanastasiou, E. (2006) investigated the apparent link between teachers' desires and the benefits they perceive from teaching. According to Hongying (2008), job satisfaction is the sum of a teacher's feelings about their job and the circumstances in which they work. A school's teachers are its most asset. They are the pivotal individuals

in every school reform effort. A high-quality education system can only be provided by qualified educators. Sharma and Jyoti (2009). According to Bolin (2007), the key to effective teaching and learning is a motivated and knowledgeable teaching staff, as well as subject matter expertise and pedagogical competence.

Job satisfaction is the emotional reaction that workers have to their work because of comparing the actual results to their expected outcomes. Satisfaction with one's employment is "an index of preference for the experienced job against outside opportunities conditional on information available at time," as stated by Garboua et al. (2005). Although there is no agreed-upon definition of what constitutes "job satisfaction," the literature consistently discusses how people feel about their employment or various parts of their work. The development of an organization's workforce as well as its employees depends on job satisfaction. Sousa-Poza (2000) found that workers are more likely to be satisfied with their jobs when there is congruence between the inputs (such as education, working time, and effort) and the outputs (such as salary, benefits, status, task significance, and working conditions) of their jobs. The organizational commitment of a teacher represents their multifaceted psychological attachment to the specific school to which they belong. According to (Mosadeghrad et al., 2008) An employee believes it is ethically correct to stay with a specific company because they feel it is the proper thing to do. The term "teacher organizational commitment" refers to educators' eagerness to fully immerse themselves in the school community. Teachers' levels of organizational commitment might be either high or very low. Teachers who are highly devoted to their work are much less likely to quit or skip class than their less dedicated counterparts, who often skip class to pursue other, more enticing interests, such as relocating to a city to be nearer to their family (Werang et al., 2015).

Several studies have shown that when people are happy in their jobs, they perform better (e.g., Altinoz et al., 2012; Ayele, 2014; Ismail and Razak, 2016; Malik et al., 2010). According to Ayele (2014), there is a robust and positive relationship between teachers' organizational commitment and their work happiness. According to Ayele (2014), a strong correlation between teachers' organizational commitment and their work satisfaction was also found. Ismail and Razak (2016) reached a similar conclusion, arguing that administrators' capacity to manage employees' job satisfaction—both intrinsically and extrinsically—has inspired workers to become more invested in the business.

Synthesis:

According to the literature, the researchers gathered, many studies have shown that student leaders' commitment and job satisfaction can be influenced by their professors' or teachers' commitment and job satisfaction. However, some studies also stated other areas or factors unrelated to the variables, such as external motivation. Nevertheless, the dedication and work satisfaction of the professors, according to the researchers, still significantly influence the student leaders' capacity to serve their fellow classmates and develop the organization. Additionally, based on the critical points of the literature, professors serve as role models. If they are dedicated to their work and are happy, they will educate and mentor their students and encourage the student leaders to grow as leaders.

Being a student leader is challenging, but if they have strong connections with their superiors or fellow student officers and a good and hands-on superior who is passionately and devoted to supporting them in their extracurricular goals, their work performance will improve. According to research, this will encourage individuals to make a stronger commitment to serving others and make them feel fulfilled since they are valued.

Methodology

Research Design

The research framework used for this study is quantitative technique, which is widely used in the social sciences. To investigate economic, social, and psychological processes by examining numerical patterns, it is necessary to follow a certain set of assumptions, methods, and tactics. A variety of numerical data is collected in quantitative research. Researchers may perform basic to very complex statistical studies on collected quantitative data to aggregate it, reveal linkages among it, or compare it to other aggregated data. In contrast to qualitative research, quantitative research makes use of procedures like experiments, systematic observations, or surveys. In 2014, Coghlan and Brydon-Miller published a study. Most quantitative outcome studies use statistical approaches to gather numerical data from the study's participants in the social sciences. Researchers and statisticians use quantity-specific theoretical frameworks and frameworks in this research approach (Pritha Bhandari, 2020).

Instead of focusing on direct cause-and-effect links, correlational designs systematically investigate the nature of associations, or correlations, between and among variables. Using these designs, we can see whether there is a correlation between two or more variables when we modify one of them. Finding the intensity, direction, degree, and size of a connection or link is what correlations are all about. The variables and their inherent correlations are described in descriptive correlational studies (Sousa et al., 2007).

Respondents

Members of the psychology faculty and student government are the subjects of this survey. College student leaders, including the President, Vice President (Internal and External), Secretary, Treasurer, Auditor, PRO, Chief Layout Artist, Junior Layout Artist, Marketing Officers, Business Manager, and Batch Representatives (From First Year to Fourth Year), make up the EAC Psychology Society Organization. The Psychology Department is composed of Four (4) Full-Time Assistant Professors and Two (2) Part-time

Professors.

Instruments

The Organizational Commitment Questionnaire - Research has shown that the OCQ is the gold standard for measuring employee dedication to their company (Mowday, Steers, and Porter, 1979). In this 15-item survey, you'll find 7-point scales ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree" for each topic. Data from many different types of businesses and occupations was used to verify the OCQ.

Job Satisfaction the Job Diagnostic Survey (JDS) - Hackman and Oldham provide insight into an employee's level of work satisfaction and intrinsic motivation. work autonomy, task importance, task identity, task variation, and feedback are the five essential aspects of a work that the measure evaluates. Evaluated as well are three mental states postulated to mediate the connection between these core features and the results achieved on the job. Lastly, this action satisfies a fundamental human need for professional success. The Job Demand Survey (JDS) uses a 7-point grading system for each of its 80 categories.

Procedure

Researchers used a reliable online platform that is often used for academic purposes, such as research and online classrooms, since it would have been exceedingly difficult and improbable to conduct the research instrument in person due to the pandemic. The participants were provided with the necessary instruments using the Google Docs area of the Google Apps. As part of its free, web-based Google Docs Editors suite, Google includes Google Forms, a survey administration tool. Included in the service are Google Docs, Sheets, Slides, Drawings, Sites, and Keep. The only way to access Google Forms is via a web browser. The forms may be filled out and submitted by participants using a variety of mobile devices, including smartphones, tablets, and desktop computers (Technopedia, 2017).

Following collection of all participant data for this research, the data will be appropriately processed using appropriate statistical methods. Based on the factors that were polled, the unique distribution of participants is determined using the percentage distribution and frequency. When you look at a data set with a percentage frequency distribution, you can see what proportion of observations there are for each data point or cluster. One of its many applications is the representation of data in terms of the relative frequency of survey replies. Tables, bar graphs, and pie charts are common ways to show percentage frequency distributions. Making a percentage frequency distribution requires knowing how many observations are to be represented, then counting how many observations are in each data point or cluster, and finally dividing that total by the number of observations (Lavrakas, 2008). Coefficients of Pearson correlation was calculated in order to investigate the pertinent correlations. A measure of the relationship (rather than the difference) between two quantitative variables (interval or ratio) and the degree to which they coincide is the Pearson correlation coefficient (r), also called the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient. This means that the two variables are linearly related, meaning that changes in one variable correspond to changes in the other. The Pearson correlation coefficient, also known as Pearson's r , is the most popular and extensively used measure of correlation in the scientific community for assessing relationships between variables. Other correlation coefficients that have been developed for this purpose include the phi correlation coefficient, point-biserial correlation, Spearman's rho, partial correlation, and part correlation (Allen, 2017).

Ethical Considerations

All those involved provide their informed permission. An informed consent form that details the methods, potential advantages, and hazards, how to access the study findings, counseling services that are available, the availability of volunteer involvement, and the contact information for the researchers involved. An explanation given prior to the commencement of the instrumentation phase; participants briefed on the study's goals and methodology. In accordance with the data privacy laws of the Philippines, the researchers reassured the participants that any pertinent personal data they divulged would be treated with the utmost respect. This study was also predicated on a pledge of secrecy and a commitment to following all applicable ethical guidelines.

Results and Discussion

I. Profile of the Participants

Table 1. A Synopsis of the Members' Profiles

Table 1.1 *Age of Psychology Society Officers*

<i>Personal Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
18	1	4.76%
19	4	19.05%
20	3	14.29%
21	3	14.29%
22	9	42.86%
23	1	4.76%
Total	21	100%

Table 1.1.1 Age of Psychology Faculties

<i>Personal Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
27	1	16.67%
28	2	33.33%
29	1	16.67%
30	1	16.67%
45	1	16.67%
Total	6	100%

Table 1.2 Sex of Psychology Society Officers

<i>Personal Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	8	38.10%
Female	13	61.90%
Total	21	100%

Table 1.2.1 Sex of Psychology Faculties

<i>Personal Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	4	66.67%
Female	2	33.33%
Total	6	100%

Table 1.3 Job Title/Position (A.Y. 2019-2020)

<i>Personal Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
President	1	12.5%
Vice President	1	12.5%
Treasurer	1	12.5%
PRO	1	12.5%
Chief Layout Artist	1	12.5%
Business Manager	2	25%
Batch Representative	1	12.5%
Total	8	100%

Table 1.3.1 Job Title/Position (A.Y. 2020-2021)

<i>Personal Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
President	1	12.5%
Vice President-Internal	1	12.5%
Vice President-External	1	12.5%
PRO	1	12.5%
Auditor	1	12.5%
Chief Layout Artist	1	12.5%
Batch Representative	2	25%
Total	8	100%

Table 1.3.2 Job Title/Position (A.Y. 2021-2022)

<i>Personal Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
President	1	12.5%
Vice President-External	1	12.5%
Secretary	1	12.5%
Treasurer	1	12.5%
PRO	1	12.5%
Chief Layout Artist	1	12.5%
Batch Representative	2	25%
Total	8	100%

Table 1.3.3 Job Title/Position (A.Y. 2022-2023)

<i>Personal Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
President	1	14.29%
Vice President-External	1	14.29%
Secretary	1	14.29%
Treasurer	1	14.29%
Auditor	1	14.29%
Marketing Officer	1	14.29%
Batch Representative	1	14.29%
Total	7	100%

Table 1.3.4 *Job Title/Position of Professors*

<i>Personal Profile</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Assistant Professor I	5	83.33%
Professor	1	16.67%
Total	6	100%

Note. The tables present the frequency and percentage distribution of the 21 psychology society officers and 6 psychology professors of a specific private institution from 2019-2022.

This study included 21 psychology society officers with ages range from 18 to 23 years old and 6 psychology professors with ages range from 27 to 45 years old of a specific private institution, Under the age of twenty-two, the majority of the students that took part in this study were (42.86%) and the majority of the professors who participated in this research are under the age of 28 (33.33%). Most of the students who participated in this research are female with 61.90% and male with 38.10% and most of the professors who took part in this study are male with 66.67% and female with 33.33%. In addition, the table displays the participants' job title/position; according to the findings, the majority of participants on A.Y 2019-2020 is Business Manager with 25%, followed by A.Y 2020-2021 Batch Representatives with 25%, A.Y 2021-2022 Batch Representatives with 25%, and 14.29% for President, Vice President-External, Secretary, Treasurer, Auditor, Marketing Officer and Batch Representative on A.Y 2022-2023. The most common job title for psychology professors in this participant group is assistant professor I (83.33%).

II. Respondents Rate their Commitment

Table 2.1 *Commitment of Psychology Society Officers*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Ranking</i>
Question 1	6.48	0.68	Strongly Agree	Very High	3
Question 2	6.33	0.80	Strongly Agree	Very High	5
Question 3	5.00	2.41	Slightly Agree	Slightly High	10
Question 4	5.57	1.08	Agree	High	9
Question 5	5.90	1.04	Agree	High	7
Question 6	6.57	0.98	Strongly Agree	Very High	1
Question 7	3.71	1.95	Neutral	Neutral	12
Question 8	6.43	0.87	Strongly Agree	Very High	4
Question 9	4.81	1.60	Slightly Agree	Slightly High	11
Question 10	6.48	0.93	Strongly Agree	Very High	3
Question 11	5.86	1.59	Agree	High	8
Question 12	5.86	1.62	Agree	High	8
Question 13	6.52	0.75	Strongly Agree	Very High	2
Question 14	6.29	0.90	Strongly Agree	Very High	6
Question 15	6.57	1.36	Strongly Agree	Very High	1
Average	5.89	0.77	Agree	High	

Legend: 6.16-7.00 Very High, 5.30-6.15, Slightly High, 4.44-5.29 High, 3.58-4.43 Neutral, 2.72-3.57 Low, 1.86-2.71 Slightly Low, 1.00-1.85 Very Low

With a mean score of 6.57, respondents in statements 6 and 15 of the Psychology Society Officers' commitment strongly agree that they are proud to be a part of the private institution's organization, but they also strongly agree that choosing to work for this organization was a poor decision.

Table 2.1.1 *Commitment of Psychology Professors*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Ranking</i>
Question 1	6.17	1.17	Strongly Agree	Very High	1
Question 2	5.50	1.22	Agree	High	3
Question 3	3.17	2.14	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Low	8
Question 4	5.50	1.05	Agree	High	3
Question 5	5.17	1.17	Slightly Agree	Slightly High	4
Question 6	5.67	1.03	Agree	High	2
Question 7	3.33	1.63	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Low	7
Question 8	5.17	0.98	Slightly Agree	Slightly High	4
Question 9	3.00	1.10	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Low	9
Question 10	5.50	1.05	Agree	High	3
Question 11	3.17	1.33	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Low	8
Question 12	3.17	1.83	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Low	8
Question 13	5.50	1.38	Agree	High	3
Question 14	4.50	4.25	Slightly Agree	Slightly High	5
Question 15	4.00	1.26	Neutral	Neutral	6
Average	4.57	0.54	Slightly Agree	Slightly High	

Legend: 6.16-7.00 Very High, 5.30-6.15, Slightly High, 4.44-5.29 High, 3.58-4.43 Neutral, 2.72-3.57 Low, 1.86-2.71 Slightly Low, 1.00-1.85 Very Low

With a mean score of 6.17, respondents in statement 1 of the commitment of psychology professors strongly believe that they are prepared to go above and beyond to assist the private institution utilized in this research succeed.

Table 2.2 Satisfaction of Psychology Society Officers

Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
Question 1	5.95	1.02	Agree	High	10
Question 2	6.33	0.91	Strongly Agree	Very High	8
Question 3	6.43	1.08	Strongly Agree	Very High	7
Question 4	5.00	1.73	Slightly Agree	Slightly High	14
Question 5	5.81	1.29	Agree	High	11
Question 6	6.10	1.04	Agree	High	9
Question 7	3.90	1.51	Neutral	Neutral	16
Question 8	5.71	0.78	Agree	High	12
Question 9	4.52	1.97	Slightly Agree	Slightly High	15
Question 10	6.62	0.59	Strongly Agree	Very High	3
Question 11	6.57	0.75	Strongly Agree	Very High	4
Question 12	6.48	0.81	Strongly Agree	Very High	6
Question 13	6.48	0.93	Strongly Agree	Very High	6
Question 14	6.67	0.66	Strongly Agree	Very High	2
Question 15	6.52	0.87	Strongly Agree	Very High	5
Question 16	5.38	1.69	Agree	High	13
Question 17	6.43	0.87	Strongly Agree	Very High	7
Question 18	5.95	1.20	Agree	High	10
Question 19	6.71	0.46	Strongly Agree	Very High	1
Question 20	6.52	0.60	Strongly Agree	Very High	5
Question 21	6.57	0.75	Strongly Agree	Very High	4
Average	6.03	0.57	Agree	High	

Legend: 6.16-7.00 Very High, 5.30-6.15, Slightly High, 4.44-5.29 High, 3.58-4.43 Neutral, 2.72-3.57 Low, 1.86-2.71 Slightly Low, 1.00-1.85 Very Low

With a mean score of 6.71, respondents to statement 19 of the Psychology Society Officers satisfaction survey highly believe that having the opportunity to assist others while at work is fulfilling.

Table 2.2.1 Satisfaction of Psychology Professors

Indicators	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
Question 1	5.50	1.38	Agree	High	2
Question 2	5.00	1.79	Slightly Agree	Slightly High	4
Question 3	5.67	1.21	Agree	High	1
Question 4	3.33	1.75	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Low	11
Question 5	4.83	1.83	Slightly Agree	Slightly High	5
Question 6	4.67	1.75	Slightly Agree	Slightly High	6
Question 7	3.50	1.52	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Low	10
Question 8	4.17	1.72	Neutral	Neutral	9
Question 9	3.50	1.64	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Low	10
Question 10	4.17	1.33	Neutral	Neutral	9
Question 11	4.50	1.22	Slightly Agree	Slightly High	7
Question 12	4.67	2.16	Slightly Agree	Slightly High	6
Question 13	4.50	1.97	Slightly Agree	Slightly High	7
Question 14	5.33	1.21	Agree	High	3
Question 15	4.33	1.86	Neutral	Neutral	8
Question 16	4.50	1.52	Slightly Agree	Slightly High	7
Question 17	5.33	1.21	Agree	High	3
Question 18	4.17	1.72	Neutral	Neutral	9
Question 19	5.50	1.38	Agree	High	2
Question 20	5.00	0.89	Slightly Agree	Slightly High	4
Question 21	4.50	1.97	Slightly Agree	Slightly High	7
Average	4.60	1.10	Slightly Agree	Slightly High	

Legend: 6.16-7.00 Very High, 5.30-6.15, Slightly High, 4.44-5.29 High, 3.58-4.43 Neutral, 2.72-3.57 Low, 1.86-2.71 Slightly Low, 1.00-1.85 Very Low

The respondents agree that they get a tremendous feeling of personal pleasure when they do a good job in statement 3 of the satisfaction of psychology professors, which has the highest mean score of 5.67.

III. Relationship between Commitment and Satisfaction of the Student Leaders and Psychology Professors

Table 3.1 Relationship between Commitment and Satisfaction of Psychology Society Officers

	Commitment			
	Pearson r	p-value	Degree of Correlation	Remarks
Satisfaction	0.67	0.000	Strong	Significant

*Significant at .05

Officers of the Psychology Society's level of dedication and happiness are shown in Table 3.1. According to the results, there is a statistically significant correlation between respondents' levels of commitment and their level of satisfaction (Pearson $r=0.67$, $p=0.000$). Reject the null hypothesis; the calculated value is significant. Thus, it is reasonable to assume that the level of pleasure felt by the Psychology Society Officers of a certain private institution is significantly correlated with their level of dedication.

Table 3.1.1 *Relationship between Commitment and Satisfaction of Psychology Professors*

	Commitment		Degree of Correlation	Remarks
	Pearson r	p -value		
Satisfaction	0.18	0.729	Very Weak	Not Significant

*Significant at .05

The correlation between psychology professors' dedication and their level of job satisfaction is shown in Table 3.1.1. A Pearson r -value of 0.18 and a p -value of 0.729 indicate that there is no statistically significant link between commitment and respondents' levels of satisfaction. We accept the null hypothesis since the calculated result is not significant. So, it's safe to say that there's no correlation between commitment and happiness among psychology professors at any one private university.

Table 3.1.2 *Relationship between Commitment and Satisfaction of Psychology Society Officers and Psychology Professors*

	Psychology Society Officers and Psychology Professors		Degree of Correlation	Remarks
	Pearson r	p -value		
Commitment	0.12	0.825	Very Weak	Not Significant
Satisfaction	-0.65	0.166	Strong	Not Significant

*Significant at .05

Table 3.1.2 shows the relationship between commitment of Psychology Society Officers and Psychology Professors. The analysis revealed that commitment of Psychology Society Officers has no significant relationship to the commitment of the Psychology Professors with Pearson r 0.12 and p -value of 0.825. Take the null hypothesis as true because the calculated value is insignificant. Officers' dedication to the field of psychology does not seem to correlate with that of psychology professors at any one private university.

In addition, it also shows that the relationship between satisfaction of Psychology Society Officers and Psychology Professors. The analysis revealed that satisfaction of Psychology Society Officers has no significant relationship to the satisfaction of the Psychology Professors with Pearson r -0.65 and p -value of 0.166. Take the null hypothesis as true because the calculated value is insignificant. To conclude, there is no correlation between the happiness of psychology professors at a particular private university and the happiness of psychology society officers.

Table 4.0 *Differences between Commitment and Satisfaction of Psychology Society Officers and Psychology Professors*

	p -value	Remarks
Commitment (Psychology Society Officers and Psychology Professors)	0.000	Significant
Satisfaction (Psychology Society Officers and Psychology Professors)	0.023	Significant

*Significant at .05

Table 4.0 shows the differences between commitment of Psychology Society Officers and Psychology Professors. The analysis revealed that commitment of Psychology Society Officers has a significant difference to the commitment of the Psychology Professors with a p -value of 0.000. Furthermore, the analysis also revealed that satisfaction of Psychology Society Officers has a significant difference to the satisfaction of the Psychology Professors with a p -value of 0.023, do not accept the null hypothesis. Thus, it is possible to deduce that the commitment and satisfaction of Psychology Society Officers has a significant difference to the commitment and satisfaction of the Psychology Professors of specific private institution.

Conclusion

The Psychology Society Organization allows those in their third or fourth year to hold the most important positions in the organization, including those of President, Vice President (internal and external), Secretary, PRO, Business Manager, and Treasurer, as they are at a stage where they are responsible and mature enough to handle such a significant role in the organization. As a result, most of the participants in this study were under the age of 22. Additionally, the average Professor participant is 28 years old, which is not too different from the average age of the other respondents, who are between the ages of 27 and 29. The mentor and founder of the psychology program at the private institution used in this study is someone above the age of 45. Most of the female participants in this study were students, whereas most of the male participants were professors. This is because most of the students in the institution who are enrolled in psychology courses are female, hence more women than men participated in this study. In addition, because most individuals who applied to the university were men, most of the professors are men. The majority of participants on A.Y. 2019-2020

held the position of business manager, followed by batch representatives on A.Y. 2020-2021 and A.Y. 2021-2022, and president, vice president-external, secretary, treasurer, auditor, marketing officer, and batch representative on A.Y. 2022-2023, the results show that the organization has different job titles, new job titles, or less job titles depending on the academic year because Psychology Society advisers change every academic year. The most common job title for psychology professors in this participant group is assistant professor I since most of them have master's degrees and not yet Ph.D. holders, which is the required education for the position.

Although the Psychology Society Officers firmly concur that it makes them proud to represent the private institution's organization because they are also involved in setting up the psychology department, the researchers conclude that we can't ignore the fact that they also firmly concur that choosing to work for this organization was a grave error on their part because of the poor management by the school itself, they don't get a support outside the psychology department that is why they continue to question whether the school should be recommended to other students. Even though they don't receive enough support, psychology professors agree that they are willing to go above and beyond what is usually necessary to ensure the success of the private institution used in this study. Even though they don't receive enough support, professors still give their all for the institution's good because that is what professionalism entails. Additionally, they are working for the benefit of the students to provide them what they are deserve.

The opportunity to help others while at work, according to officers of the psychology society, is rewarding for them because of the gratitude they receive from their co fellow psychology students as well as the compliments they receive from their superiors (Psychology Department Head and Psychology Society Adviser) and according to psychology professors, when they carry out their responsibilities well within the organization, they experience a great deal of personal fulfillment. This is also related to the appreciation they receive from psychology students; each time they receive positive feedback or an appreciation message, they feel good about their work and become more motivated to do their jobs.

The researchers come to the conclusion that the Psychology Society Officers' commitment and satisfaction are linked because they need to be passionate and dedicated to their work in order to commit to it. If their work is successful, they will receive compliments from others, which they view as a reward for their efforts since they do not receive a salary for their service as officers. In addition, professors of psychology who are dedicated to their work but yet seek other things that would make them happy find that there is no correlation between their commitment to their work and their level of fulfillment. They are performing their duties out of need, and while they are pleased with the students' messages of thanks, it is still fact that the higher management does not recognize their efforts, which will bring dissatisfaction.

The researchers came to the conclusion that regardless of how motivated professors are to influence the officers, it is still up to the students to decide whether or not they will commit or be satisfied with their work. Similarly, regardless of how dedicated the Psychology society Officers are to serving the organization, if the Professors are not happy or satisfied in their job, it will not have an impact on the attitude, behavior, or decision.

Based on the findings of the study, several recommendations have been formulated: The psychology department continues to offer a seminar, training, or program so that the professors of psychology and the officials of the psychological society may stay informed and advance their skills.

The study also recommends counseling sessions, interviews, or "kamustahan" to help employees and cops live healthy lives so they can support psychology students more.

Every semester, the psychology department will keep track of the performance survey results so that psychology professors and psychology society officers may decide whether to keep the work as is or modify it to better meet the needs of psychology students. The department might also develop a special program that expresses the students' gratitude in order to keep their enthusiasm to work for the institution.

The psychology department organizes professional team-building activities so that Psychology Society Officers and Psychology Professors can communicate effectively at least twice every semester.

The study's findings should help other researchers who are interested in performing a similar study to improve their methods or even to challenge them in order to find other factors impacting the presented variables. It's also suggested to spread out the research's geographic scope.

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